

Results One-Minute-Paper and my answers

What was most interesting?

- Number-Estimation-Question
- Determine Order Method (as a selfstudy method)
- I like this workshop, it's full of new information, also it's joyful and helpful.
- Methods of how keep students active.
- I learned methods of activating in classroom for large and small groups + they very easy althrough I thought before this is very difficult.

Your questions:

1) Is it possible to apply all of these methods in teaching physics?

Yes, I think so, my ideas:

- *Show similarities* at the beginning to get an overview.
- *Solution by raising a hand* for questions to the students about knowledge or ideas about concepts.
- *Number-Estimation Question*, when there are interesting number-facts.
- *Call-out Question*, when you want to collect ideas about a topic.
- *Headstand method*: What can I do, that ... does not works?
- *Buzz Group*: E.g. Discuss the most interesting aspects! Which formula is best to use? How is these theory/ concept useful in practice? ...
- *Determine order*: You can use it, if there are processes with clear steps in Physics!?
- *Solution in the row of seats*: To let the students repeat important aspects of a topic.
- *One-Minute-Paper*: As an easy and fast feedback method

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2) Relationship between Content/Knowledge and method?

In my opinion, methods are vehicles for content/knowledge or tools. They work together, they are not mutually exclusive! Method comes from the Latin *methodos*, which means the way. There are different methods of offering content to students. In each case, it is important to consider which goal I want to achieve, i.e. which skills I want to promote.

3) I don't have questions, everything is clear.

Fine 😊

4) How to keep "lost"/ uninterested students active in the lesson?

Focus on the motivated, be self-motivated even if some students aren't. And you can ask what they need to generate more interest.

What I do at the beginning of a new course is to explain to the students that they are primarily responsible for their learning success. If the students are still unmotivated, I just accept that and don't mind. I am responsible for solving a problem when more than half are unmotivated.

5) Can we use some of these methods for formative assessment?

With these methods, the focus is on short activation and exchange. There is an overview of alternative examination procedures from a university in Munich that are actually used as examinations here at universities in Germany. Unfortunately, the documents are written in German, but I can send them to anyone who is interested.